

O'ZBEK TILI TARIXI

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ANNOTATSIYA: O'zbek tili uyg'ur tili bilan birgalikda qarluq tili guruhiga kiradi. Qarluq tili tarixiy jihatdan O'rta Osiyo guruhiga, ayniqsa, g'arbiy xun shaxobchasiga kirgan tillar bilan oiladoshdir.

Kalit so'zlar: badiiy matn, adabiy-estetik tahlil, sharhli o'qish, izohli o'qish, adabiy o'qish.

XI asrdan keyingi O'rta Osiyo turkiy tillari, shu jumladan, o'zbek adabiy tilining rivojlanishidagi ma'lum davrlarni belgilash mumkin. Til tarixini o'rganishdagi eng muhim masalalardan biri – davrlashtirishdir. Davrlashtirish uchun o'zbek tili va unga urug'dosh bo'lgan turkiy tillarning kelib chiqishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari, o'zaro munosabatlari aniqlanishi lozim.

Ma'lumki, davrlashtirish turkiy tillarning tasnifi bilan ham bog'liqdir. Tasnif ma'lum darajada tillar tarixini davrlashtirish demakdir. Chunki tasnifda ham, davrlashtirishda ham bir xil printsipga amal qilinadi.

Turkiy tillarning tasnifi XI asrda M. Koshg'ariy tomonidan berilgan bo'lsa ham XIX asrgacha bu tillarning mukammal tasnifi yaratilmagan yedi. XIX asrdan boshlab turkiy tillarni rus olimlari tasnif qila boshladilar. Til tarixini o'rganishdagi yeng muhim masalalardan biri — davrlashtirishdir. Davrlashtirish uchun o'zbek tili va unga urug'dosh bo'lgan turkiy tillarning kelib chiqishi, taraqqiyot bosqichlari, o'zaro munosabatlari aniqlanishi lozim.

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Ularning ba'zilari turkiy tillarni hududiy – jo'g'rofiy jihatdan tasnif qilsa, boqshalari tshsharning bir xil lingvistik beyagisiga asoslanadi. Uchinchilarida turkiy tillar tarixi xalq tarixi bilan yetarlicha bog'lanmaydi. Shular ichida N.A.Baskov tasnifi ancha mukammal tuyuladi.

Shuni aytish kerakki, lingvistik adabiyotlarda eski o'zbek tilining xususiyatlari haqida gap borganda buyuk Alisher Navoiy asarlariga asoslaniladi, chunki Alisher Navoiy o'zbek xalqining ulug' mutafakkiri, atoqli shoiri va ulkan tilshunosi bo'lishi bilan birga yeski o'zbek adabiy tiliga asos solgan, uni shakllantirish va rivojlantirish ishiga hammadan ko'ra ko'p hissa qo'shgan bir siymodir. Shuning uchun ham eski o'zbek adabiy tilining shakllanishi va taraqqiy yetishi haqqoniy ravishda Alisher Navoiyning tabarruk nomi bilan bog'liqdir.

«Haqiqatdan ham Alisher Navoiyning tili butun bir davrning tilidir, butun bir xalqning adabiy tilidir» (X.Doniyorov. Alisher Navoiy tilining dialektal asoslarini o'rganish masalasiga doir. A.N. va adabiy ta'sir masalasi. T, 1968.279).

Ma'lumki, Alisher Navoiy har qancha ulug' siymo bo'lishiga qaramay, u ham ma'lum bir xalqning vakili bo'lgan va uning tili ko'p shevalarni birlashtirganligi bilan birga, ma'lum shevaga ham tayangan, uning tilida o'sha ma'lum sheva yoki shevalarning izi boshqalarinikiga qaraganda ko'prok aks yetgan. Demak, endi Alisher Navoiy tiliga asos bo'lgan sheva qaysi sheva edi degan masala kun tartibida ko'ndalang bo'ladi.

Bu masala olimlar o'rtasida tortishuvga sabab bo'lmoqda. Bunga Zahriddin Muhammad Boburning Alisher Navoiy tili Andijon shevasiga mos kelsa-da, degan fikri asos bo'lmoqda. Ma'lumki, Bobur har tomonlama bilimli, olim kishi bo'lgan. U o'zining «Boburnoma» degan mashhur asarida o'sha davrdagi ijtimoiy tuzum, siyosiy voqealar, adabiy hayot va boshqa ko'pgina sohalarni ilmiy analiz qilib berish bilan birga, til sohasida ham ajoyib fikrlar aytgan. Bobur Andijon haqida gapirib Shunday deydi: «Eli turkdur. Shahr va bozorisida turkiy bilmas kishi yo'stur. Yelining lafzu qalam bila rostdur. Ani uchun kim Mir Alisher Navoiyning muzannafoti, bovujudkim Hirida nash'u noma topibdur, bu til biladir» (1960. 60-bet).

Xususan, Navoiydan keyin tez orada mamlakatning Temuriylar qo'lidan ketganligi va shu munosabat bilan bog'liq holda avval Dashti qipchoqda yashab kelgan va bu erdagi aholiga nisbatan son jihatdan ko'proq bo'lgan o'zbeklarning (qipchoq va ko'chmanchi o'zbeklarning) bu yerga kelib o'rnashishi va bu erdagi aholi bilan asrlar davomida aralashib ketganligi hisobga olinsa, Avdijon

shevasida, shuningdek, boshqa o'zbek shevalarida ham o'tgan davr ichida qanchalik kuchli va katta o'zgarishlar sodir bo'lganini tushunib olish qiyin bo'lmaydi.

Professor V.Abdullayevning ko'rsatishicha, Alisher Navoiy Samarqandda ikki yil yemas, balki 4-5 yil bo'lgan. Bu davr ichida deb ta'kidlaydi X.Doniyorov, u V.Abdullayev aytganidek, Samarqandning janub tomonlaridagina yemas, balki uning sharq tomonlarida, ya'ni Andijon tomonlarida ham bo'lganligi yehtimol. O'sha davrdagi shahar shevalari ichida andijon shevasi adabiy tilga yaqin (qalam bila rost) shevalardan biri bo'lgan va Samarqand shevasi yesa, o'sha paytda temuriylar davlatining poytaxtlaridan birining shevasi va sharqiy shevalardan biri sifatida hirot shevasiga nisbatan Andijon shevasiga ancha yaqin bo'lgan bo'lishi mumkin. Shuningdek, o'sha davrda Andijon va Samarqandning aholilari ham ancha kuchli bo'lgan. Alisher Navoiy Andijon shevasi bilan ham bolalik vaqtlaridanoq, o'sha Hirotdayoq tanisha boshlagan bo'lishi mumkin.

Chunki Hirotga Avdijon tomondan juda ko'p ustalar, navkarlar, kosiblar va boshqa toifalarning borganligi, ular ichida ayniqsa, andijonlik shoirlar va mashsho'slar yaxshi obro'ga yega bo'lgan. Demak, «qalam bila rost» sheva sifatida Andijon shevasi hali Alisher maktabga qatnab yurgan vaqtlaridayoq uning e'tiborini tortgan bo'lishi mumkin.

Alisher Navoiy Andijon shevasi bilan hali go'dakligida oila muhitidayoq tanilgan bo'lishi ham mumkin, chunki Alisherni tarbiyalaganlardan yoki unga qarindosh bo'lganlardan birortasining andijonlik bo'lishi yehtimoldan tashqari, Alisherning ota-onalari, uning oilasidagi kattalar va saroy kishilari, shu jumladan, barloslar gaplashgan sheva asosan o'sha davrdagi Shahrisabz, Kitob shevasi bo'lgan, chunki u yerlar barloslarning makoni bo'lgan. Shunday ekan Shahrisabz-kitob shevasi o'sha vaqtda Andijon shevasiga, Hirot katta Samarqand va Buxoro shevalariga nisbatan ham yaqin turgan bo'lishi yehtimoldan uzoq yemas.

Alisher Navoiy tilining Andijon shevasiga mos bo'lganligini isbotlovchi dalillardan biri shundan iboratki, o'sha vaqtda Andijon va Shahrisabz-Kitob shevalari o'rtasidagina yemas, Andijon bilan Samarqand va Buxoro hatto, Hirot shevalari o'rtasida ham keskin farqlar unchalik bo'lmagan, balki ular o'rtasida o'xshashliklar ancha ko'p bo'lgan. A.Navoiyning ta'kidlashicha, faqat Xorazm shevasigina boshqa shevalardan ajralib turgan. Lekin keyinchalik mamlakatda yuz

bergan ijtimoiy-siyosiy yetnik o'zgarishlar tufayli xususan, Alisher Navoiy vafotidan keyin tez vaqt ichida mamlakatning Dashti qipchoqdan kelgan o'zbeklar qo'liga o'tish va ularning butun mamlakat buylab, boshqa o'zbeklar bilan aralashib ketishlari natijasida), o'sha vaqtda bir-biri bilan yaqin bo'lgan shevalar asta-sekin boshqa shevalar bilan qo'yilishi, murakkab interatsiya va differentsiatsiya holatlarini boshdan kechirishlari natijasida ularning har qaysisi har xil yangi xususiyatlar kasb yetgan. Shuning natijasida ular bir-biridan uzoqlasha borgan. Shuning uchun ham A.Navoiy asarlari tili hozirgi Andijon shevasiga o'xshamay qolganligi tasodifiy yemas. Shunday qilib, Alisher Navoiy asarlari tili Andijon shevasi tilidagi «y»lovchi shahar shevalariga mos keladi, chunki Navoiy zamonida y-lovchi tipdagi sha'kar markaz shevalari umumxalq o'zbek tilining negizini tashkil yetgan.

Shahar markaz shevalariga yesa Andijon, Namangan, Qo'qon, Toshkent, Buxoro, Samarqand, Shahrisabz, Kitob kabi shevalar kirar yedi. Lekin shu bilan barobar yeski o'zbek adabiy tili boqsha o'zbek shevalarining ham, chunonchi, janubiy Xorazm shevalarining va qipchoq shevalarining zarur yelementlarini qabul qilgan. Bu jihatdan she'riy asarlar tili xarakterlidir. She'riy asarlar tilida proza asarlari tiliga nisbatan o'g'uz shevalarining ta'siri kuchliroqdir.

Ушбу мақолада ўқув луғатларининг умумий луғатлардан нафақат ҳажми, балки ундаги сўзларнинг танланиш мезонлари, луғат қисмларининг таркиби, жойлашуви – мегаструктураси билан ҳам фарқланиши, синоним ўқув луғатлар луғат мақоласи таркибида лексикографик пометалар (турли қисқартмалар, белгилар)га кам ўрин берилганлиги муҳокама қилинади.¹

This article is dedicated to the research of Adjusted meanings of Moral-spiritual concept defining units in the Uzbek language. And also analyzed the semantic analysis of grammatical shape lexemes of specialized meaning and provide a corresponding recommendation for lexicographical practice in the Uzbek language is one of the actual challenges of linguistics as today's challenge.²

¹ Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУҒАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

² Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. *ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies*, 5(7), 40-45.

Корпус лингвистикасида семантик разметка, унинг теглар тизими, тег категориялари, семантик теглаш муаммолари, кўпмаънолилик ва омонимлик муаммосини ечиш масаласига оид қатор тадқиқотлар вужудга келган.³

The article discusses the research methods of Uzbek language syntax. In Uzbek linguistics, syntactic phenomena have been studied in detail since the 1930s, and several syntactic theories have emerged in this regard.⁴

The article examines the first dictionary in the Turkish language Mahmud Kashgaris “Devonu lugotit turk” in terms of a dictionary in accordance with the traditions of world lexicography and argues that it is the first appearance of modern complex dictionaries in the Turkish (Uzbek) language.⁵

Now studying scientific heritage, socio-political activities and acquaintance youth charity of our above-stated ancestors is considered one of the main urgent objectives of the modern intellectuals.⁶

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.⁷

Мамлакатимиз тараққиётининг янги босқичида жамият ҳаётининг асосий негизи бўлмиш оилалар барқарор муҳитини мустаҳкамлаш ва бу масалаларда хотин-қизларнинг ўрни ва аҳамияти ошириш долзарб аҳамият касб этмоқда. Юртимиз аҳолисининг тенг

³ Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. *Oriental Art and Culture*, (III), 440-444.

⁴ Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 22-28.

⁵ Bakhriddinova, B. M. (2020). “DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK” AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (4), 981-985.

⁶ Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(05), 211-215.

⁷ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

ярмига яқинроғини ташкил этадиган хотин-қизлар жамиятнинг барча соҳаларида самарали фаолият юритмоқда.⁸

In this article are given the importance, role, types of the family in modern society. Its development from ancient times till present is widely described in this article.⁹

The widespread introduction of new pedagogical technologies in teaching students of higher educational institutions and the effective use of innovative technologies are the main support for improving the quality of education.¹⁰

The article describes in detail the basics of translation theory, the object of research, and the methods of analysis of translation theory. Opinions on the importance of translation among different peoples, the concept of translation, and its types are discussed. However, various examples of translation types are given.¹¹

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women.¹²

This article analyzes how Somerset Maugham's short story "A Friend in Need" skillfully reflects the power and value of true friendship using ethical concepts such as goodness, kindness, justice, and compassion, which are sacred to each of us.¹³

⁸ Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРИНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>

⁹ Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. *European science review*, (3-4), 69-72.

¹⁰ Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 11(01), 149-151.

¹¹ Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies*, 24(2), 35-40.

¹² Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

¹³ Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240-244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in “Tamburlaine the Great” by Christopher Marlowe.¹⁴

This article discusses an attitude to women in the past and the interpretation of the image of women in the works of some writers.¹⁵

В современном обществе все более возрастает роль иностранных языков. Знание иностранного языка дает молодежи возможность приобщиться к мировой культуре, использовать в своей деятельности потенциал обширных ресурсов глобальной сети Интернет, а также работать с информационными и коммуникационными технологиями и мультимедийными средствами обучения.¹⁶

This article deals with the heroes of the novel “Between Two Doors”, one of the most popular works of modern Uzbek literature. There is a comprehensive analysis of the female image. A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel “Between Two Doors”. The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling “Between Two Doors”, the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death.¹⁷

Har bir millat madaniyatida kasallik nomlarini ifodalovchi qarashlar mavjud bo'lib ular shu xalq dunyoqarashini, dinini, urf-odatlarini, turmush tarzini va tarixini o'zida mujassamlashtiradi. Xususan, o'zbek va ingliz xalqi amaliy nutqida rak, sil, vabo kabi xavfli kasalliklar nomi qadimda tabulashtirilgan, bunga tarixiy sabablar mavjud. Hozirgi kunda ularning davosi topilgan bo'lsada, xalqimiz “yomon xastalik,” og'ir dard,” yomon kasallik” kabi birikmalarni qo'llash bilan kifoyalanadi.¹⁸

¹⁴ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY “TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT”. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

¹⁵ Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.

¹⁶ Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. Коммуникативный метод. *Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.

¹⁷ Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book “Between Two Doors”). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

¹⁸ Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI.

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Badiiy adabiyotning qamrov darajasi keng sanaladi. Zero undagi janrlarning har biri insonning kamoloti uchun xizmat qiladi.¹⁹

В данной статье сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского.²⁰

В настоящее время глобальной социальной опасностью является угроза обнищания населения. Безработица, экономическая и социальная нестабильность, несбыточность надежд, крушение планов интенсифицируют процесс маргинализация населения.²¹

The relevance of speech and culture in the present day is considered important in linguistics and its areas of study are becoming more and more comprehensive day by day. This article will highlight the important aspects of the study of culture and national characteristics in the study of modern units of oral speech. Currently, English is widely spoken in the world community. It is the language of Advanced Science and technology, trade and cultural relations, trade and business.²²

The article is dedicated to the description of Uzbek national children's clothes of the past centuries and its modern implementation. Article describes types of clothes, its designation and modern usage.²³

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Гуландом Мирханова. (2022). СИНОНИМ СЎЗЛАР ЎҚУВ ЛУФАТИНИНГ УМУМИЙ ТУЗИЛИШИ. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 172–178. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/90>

¹⁹ Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>

²⁰ Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.

²¹ Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.

²² NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).

²³ Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.

2. Gulbahor, T. (2016). Adjusted Meanings of Moral-Spiritual Concept Defining Units. ANGLISTICUM. Journal of the Association-Institute for English Language and American Studies, 5(7), 40-45.
3. Ахмедова, Д. (2020). Семантик разметка тизимида тег гуруҳлари. Oriental Art and Culture, (III), 440-444.
4. Ergashevna, Y. N. (2021). ON METHODS OF RESEARCH OF UZBEK LANGUAGE SYNTAX. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 9(11), 22-28.
5. Bakhridinova, B. M. (2020). "DEVONU LUGOTIT TURK" AS A FIRST VIEW OF MODERN COMPLEX EDUCATIONAL DICTIONARIES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (4), 981-985.
6. Tolibjonovich, M. T. (2021). EASTERN RENAISSANCE AND ITS CULTURAL HERITAGE: THE VIEW OF FOREIGN RESEARCHERS. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(05), 211-215.
7. Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.
8. Мадумарова Зиёдахон. (2022). ЯНГИЛАНАЁТГАН ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ГЕНДЕР МУАММОЛАРИНИ БАРТАРАФ ЭТИШДА АХЛОҚИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРНИНГ ЎРНИ. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6569712>
9. Nasriddinovich, A. A. (2020). THE FEATURES OF APPEARING FAMILY IN MODERN SOCIETY. European science review, (3-4), 69-72.
10. Jamoliddinovich, U. B. (2022). FUNDAMENTALS OF EDUCATION QUALITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(01), 149-151.
11. Gafurovna, R. Z. (2021). Translation Theory: Object of Research and Methods of Analysis. International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies, 24(2), 35-40.
12. Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. International Journal of Biomedicine, 6(1), 38-40.

13. Pulatova Sabina. (2022). THE REVELATION OF VIRTUE THROUGH EVIL IN THE SHORT STORY "A FRIEND IN NEED" BY WILLIAM SOMERSET MAUGHAM. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(2), 240–244. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/100>
14. Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.
15. Muradovich, R. M. (2021). The Image of a Woman in The Work of Uzbek Writers. *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 3, 7-12.
16. Махмурова, М., Абдуллаева, Л. С., & Самадова, С. А. Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль*, 6, 72-76.
17. Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.
18. Baxronova Matluba. (2022). RUHIY KASALLIKLARNING INGLIZ ADABIYOTIDA BERILISHI. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6509637>
19. Oripova Kamola. (2022). O'ZBEK VA FRANSUZ TILLARIDAGI MAQOLLARDA JON KONSEPTINING IFODALANISHI. *Yosh Tadqiqotchi Jurnal*, 1(3), 398–408. Retrieved from <http://2ndsun.uz/index.php/yt/article/view/209>
20. Тухтаева, Ф. И., & Хамроева, Ш. Ш. (2019). Сопоставление диккенсовской концепции детства и концепции детства в произведениях Достоевского. *Мировая наука*, (5), 709-713.
21. Суяров, З. Э. (2021). СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОЕ ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ БЕДНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1175-1182.
22. NARZIYEVA, I. Z. (2021, March). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND NATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MODERN UNITS OF ORAL SPEECH (based on Uzbek and English language materials). In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-289).
23. Kadirova, N. A. (2020). UZBEK NATIONAL CHILDRENS CLOTHING AND ITS EVOLUTION. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (6), 155-157.